

Advancing Timber for the Future Built Environment

European policies influencing wood supply and demand in scenarios until 2040

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InnovaWood

The European Network
for **Wood** Research,
Innovation and Education

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82 member organisations

30 countries

EU-funded projects

European Forest Research and Innovation Ecosystem

- Delivers a Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda for forestry and the forest-based sector
- Implementation measures and stakeholder commitments co-designed in a multi-actor approach
- Preparation of the European Partnership for Forests for co-programming of future funding

Grant no. 101081788, RIA, 2022-2026

Coordinator EFI, Finland

16 partners, 3.9 mio €

cordis/101081788 | eufore.eu

Empowering climate-smart, circular, and zero-waste use of underutilized wood from the forest and building stock in the construction sector to support the New European Bauhaus

- Underutilised wood species and material streams
- Zero-waste and circular building designs
- Assessing human health and well-being aspects by co-creation activities

Grant no. 101181021, RIA, 2024-2028

Coordinator University of Gent, Belgium

13 partners, 6.8 mio €

cordis/101181021 | woodstockproject.eu

**WORLD CONFERENCE ON
TIMBER ENGINEERING 2025**
BRISBANE, AUSTRALIA

Advancing Timber for the Future Built Environment

Overview

- **Context:** Wood flows in Europe
- **Methodology**
- **Results:** Trends, EU regulations, scenarios
- **Conclusions & research needs**

“Will we have enough wood?”

Will we see a timber building boom to decarbonize the built environment?

vs.

Will forests pass the tipping points and shift from a carbon sink to a source?

Buildings as global carbon sink.

Churkina et al. 2020. *Nature Sustainability*, vol. 3, 269–276. [doi](#)

Cities as carbon sinks—classification of wooden buildings.

Amiri et al. 2020. *Env. Res. Letters* 15/094076. [doi](#)

Amazonia as a carbon source linked to deforestation and climate change.

Gatti et al. *Nature* **595**, 388–393 (2021). [doi](#)

First signs of carbon sink saturation in European forest biomass.

Nabuurs et al. *Nature Clim Change* 3, 792–796 (2013). [doi](#)

How will the EU legislate and regulate it?

EU Green Deal? Circular Bioeconomy? Competitiveness?

Wood flows in Europe

State of play

- Industrial roundwood from forest feeds primary transformation industries:
 - sawmilling, mainly converted into **EWP** (such as CLT, GLT) for the construction sector,
 - wood-based panels** (WBP), mainly for furniture,
 - pulp and paper
- EWP and WBP are promising **long-life products for decarbonization** (carbon storage, substitution).
- Demand side:** General agreement/expectation in industry that the total demand for wood in Europe will increase substantially in the long run.

Figure 1. Sankey diagram of wood flow in EU-27 by product. Adapted from European Commission, 2023.

Methodology

Research steps

1. Analysis of production statistics to show dynamics and trends in sawnwood and WBP.
2. Analysis of relevant European regulations and directives regarding expected implications on wood supply and demand.
3. Exploring future scenarios together with industry experts via workshops, surveys and interviews.

Scenarios of policy implications

Regulations
EU 2024/1991
Nature Restoration Law
EU 2018/2001
Energy from renewable sources
EU 2022/2448
Sustainability criteria for forest biomass
EU 2022/2464
Corporate sustainability reporting
EU 2010/75/EU
Industrial Emissions
EU 2021/1119
European Climate Law
EU 2818/841
LULUCF
EU 2021/2139, EU 2020/852
EU Taxonomy
COM(2022)672
Certification framework for carbon removals
EU 2024/3110
Construction Products Regulation (CPR)
EU 2018/852
Packaging and packaging waste
EU 2024/1275
Energy Performance of Buildings
EU 2014/52/EU
Environmental Impact Assessment

Trends and future projections

Long time series analysis

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 - pulp and paper
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General agreement in industry that the total demand for wood in Europe will increase substantially in the long run.

European regulations

Main observations

- European policies target a **broad range of impact areas** in industry and society, which may play a significant role in wood supply and demand.
- Expected implications:** most regulations seem to reduce supply, and to increase demand at the same time.
- Complex landscape and interplay:** difficult to foresee exact directions and decisions of future policies.

Table 2. EU regulations, main objectives and potential implications for wood supply and demand.

Regulations	Keywords of objectives	SUPPLY	DEMAND
EU 2024/1991 Nature Restoration Law	effective land and sea restoration measures	--- / [++]	0.
EU 2018/2001 Energy from renewable sources	restrictions certain wood products, cascade use of wood	---	[-] / +++
EU 2022/2448 Sustainability criteria for forest biomass	fuel from forest biomass, with mandatory monitoring	---	0.
EU 2022/2464 Corporate sustainability reporting	reporting on social and environmental impacts	---	+++
EU 2010/75/EU Industrial Emissions	reduce industrial pollution and waste	--- / [++]	+++
EU 2021/1119 European Climate Law	reduce net GHG emissions, forests for decarbonisation	--- / +++	+++
EU 2818/841 LULUCF	national forest accounting	--- / [++]	0.
EU 2021/2139, EU 2020/852 EU Taxonomy	sustainable investment framework	0.	+++
COM(2022)672 Certif. framework for carbon removals	carbon removal innovation technology	--- / [++]	+++
EU 2024/3110 Construction Products Regulation	mandatory sustainability requirements	0.	+++
EU 2018/852 Packaging and packaging waste	reduce packaging waste	0.	+++
EU 2024/1275 Energy Performance of Buildings	real estate stock with zero emissions	0.	+++
EU 2014/52/EU Environmental Impact Assessment	protection of the environment	---	0.

Classes: 0. Neutral, no impact, --- Reduce supply/demand, increase cost, +++ Increase supply/demand, improve use, [+] side effect

Case with undecided direction:

- a) if focus on forest as carbon sink > limit harvesting, reduce supply
- or b) if focus on carbon storage in products > boost supply

Potential future scenarios

Scenario 1. Increase of demand

- *Main assumption:*
EU first priorities: economic stability, energy security. Biodiversity and climate only secondary.
- Leads to **strong demand for sawnwood and EWP**, as alternative to fossil- and energy-demanding materials.
- Climate policies favouring **long-life carbon-storing wood products**.
- **Increasing competition** between wood uses (e.g. WBP vs. pulp vs. energy)

Scenario 2. Stagnation of demand

- *Main assumption:*
EU strengthens environmental regulations in line with climate targets.
- Leads to **higher restrictions** on forest harvesting.
- Introduces **complex compliance requirements, increased costs** for monitoring and administration.
- Favourable for **carbon sinks in land use/forest** (restoration, afforestation), less for wood products.
- Conflicting policies would lead to stagnation.

Other drivers beyond policy

- **Forestry practices** at operational level will remain largely conventional.
> slow implementation / change
- **National and global markets:** decisive drivers for wood industries > geopolitical tensions increase risks & instability
- **Climate change** is reshaping forests: increase of disturbances (storms, drought, fires, pest outbreaks) become severe.

Conclusions

Main findings & Research needs

- Demand increasing, supply side uncertain.
- General economy (building sector, consumers) steers demand for wood products.
 - > EU policies have only limited direct influence.

- **Need for science-based priority setting** to inform effective policies, alongside governance mechanisms capable of addressing conflicting perspectives, setting clear priorities, and fostering shared visions for the future of forests and related sectors.

- Higher market competition for raw materials:
 - > increase of domestic removals / harvesting?
 - > increase imports from outside the EU?
 - > conflicting topic: decline of wood energy?

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- **Policies supporting innovation** more circular use (reuse, reclaim, recycle) and novel material efficient wood products (small diameters, salvage wood, hardwoods).
- **Enabling regulatory framework** Standards, certifications to allow market entry

Let's innovate with wood!

And connect
wood science and engineering
with forests!

connect - share - influence

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Annex: European regulations (1)

Main target / outcome

0 Neutral impact

- Reduce supply/demand, increase cost

+ increase supply demand, improve use

Regulations	Summarised objectives	SUPPLY implications	DEMAND implications
EU 2024/1991 Nature Restoration Law	Member States must implement effective land and sea restoration measures to cover at least 20% of terrestrial and marine areas by 2030 and all degraded ecosystems by 2050, while monitoring key forest ecosystem indicators such as deadwood, forest structure, bird populations, or soil carbon.	Stricter harvesting regulations prioritizing low-impact cutting methods may reduce wood supply but enhance other forest ecosystem services.	No direct implications for the demand were expected.
EU 2018/2001 Energy from renewable sources	Overall renewable energy target of 42.5% by 2030 implies restrictions on energy production from certain wood products , promoting the principle of cascade use of wood , ending support for electric-only plants, and establishing requirements for guaranteed sustainable biomass sourcing.	A part of non-exploited wood for energy production could remain in forests. The wood supply for energy use can decrease.	Reduced competition between wood industries and energy production, with a long-term decline in wood energy use (which could remain available just in some regions) and more wood raw material becoming available for secondary products .
EU 2022/2448 Sustainability criteria for forest biomass	Guarantee sustainability criteria for producing fuel from forest biomass , with mandatory monitoring to ensure forest regeneration, protection of protected areas, minimising negative impacts on soil, biodiversity and productive capacity.	Possible limitations of forest biomass supply if criteria are not complied with, and the monitoring activities could lead to an increase of supply costs .	No direct implications for the demand were expected.
EU 2022/2464 Corporate sustainability reporting	EU companies must ensure transparency by reporting on social and environmental impacts of their commercial activities as well as the business effects of their environmental, social and governance initiatives.	Stricter rules for emissions and evaluation, monitoring and compliance with environmental standards will lead to higher operative costs and wood prices , possibly decreasing viable supply.	Innovations to reduce polluting emissions could drive industry industry and consumers shift toward more sustainable products, improving the public attitude towards the role of forests and wood products in carbon sequestration.
EU 2010/75/EU Industrial Emissions	MS must reduce industrial pollution and waste by implementing environmental permits, enforcing compliance measures, and suspending operations that repeatedly fail to meet environmental standards.	Stricter rules for emission control and adherence to environmental quality standards will reduce emissions, potentially increasing operational costs and wood prices , while enhancing ecosystem health and other forest ecosystem services.	Innovations to minimise polluting emissions could drive industry and consumers towards more sustainable products and improving public perception of the role of forests and wood products in carbon storage.

Table 2. EU regulations, main objectives and potential implications for wood supply and demand.

Annex: European regulations (2)

Main target / outcome

0 Neutral impact

- Reduce supply/demand, increase cost

+ increase supply demand, improve use

Regulations	Summarised objectives	SUPPLY implications	DEMAND implications
EU 2021/1119 European Climate Law	MS must adopt national strategies for climate change adaptation to comply with the objective to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. Forests are considered as a tool for the decarbonisation of industries/sectors supported by investment in green technology.	Focus on forest carbon sinks will limit harvesting and raise costs, reducing the available wood supply . Reversely, a focus on carbon storage in construction products will boost wood supply and lower restrictions and costs.	Increasing demand for wood and other biomass for energy and wood products carbon substitution and storage .
EU 2818/841 LULUCF	The net land carbon removal of 310 Mt CO ₂ e by 2030 obliges to develop national forest accounting plans detailing emissions/ sequestration, carbon pools, GHG, and sustainable management.	To ensure GHG emissions reduction, forest management decisions could take the direction to limit harvest intensity, limiting the available wood for production . Only if afforestation is promoted actively, the wood supply could be increased in the long term.	No direct implications for the demand were expected.
EU 2021/2139, EU 2020/852 EU Taxonomy	A voluntary market information tool to establish a sustainable investment framework through the creation of a classification system, or ‘taxonomy’, which defines environmentally sustainable economic activities.	No direct implications for the supply were expected.	The taxonomy criteria in bioenergy and wood construction can open opportunities to attract investments , in environmental reporting or marketing.
COM(2022)672 Certification framework for carbon removals	Establishment of quality criteria to facilitate investment in carbon removal innovation technology , requiring operators to ensure long-term carbon storage through monitoring and accountability measures.	It could increase the monitoring costs as a requisite for the certification, creating tension between the need to increase wood supply and increase the forest areas dedicated to carbon capture.	Sustainability competition boost demand for wood for energy and for wood products for carbon storage .
EU 2024/3110 Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	Establishes mandatory sustainability requirements for the construction products (Environmental Product Declaration) and circularity, as well as the digitalisation of the information about the environmental, structural, health and safety performance in Digital Product Passports.	No direct implications for the supply were expected.	Increasing demand for wood and EWP as a sustainable material as alternatives to fossil-based construction materials, for by-products, residues, and reused wood for the development of new construction products with potential for building design for disassembly.

Table 2. EU regulations, main objectives and potential implications for wood supply and demand.

Annex: European regulations (3)

Main target / outcome

0 Neutral impact

- Reduce supply/demand, increase cost

+ increase supply demand, improve use

Regulations	Summarised objectives	SUPPLY implications	DEMAND implications
EU 2018/852 Packaging and packaging waste	Harmonise the national measures and standards for packaging management to reduce packaging waste by promoting reuse, recycling and other forms of packaging waste valorisation. It affects solid wood packaging (pallets, crates) and packaging paper.	No direct implications for the supply were expected.	Increasing demand for more sustainable packaging, with wood as a substitute of plastics. However, the requirements for minimizing the weight and volume of packaging will imply a lower volume of wood and cellulose per unit.
EU 2024/1275 Energy Performance of Buildings	Achieve a decarbonised real estate stock with zero emissions by 2050, reducing both construction and operational greenhouse gas emissions in buildings.	No direct implications for the supply were expected.	Growing demand for more sustainable materials (pulp, wood fibres) and products (WBP) for building insulation. Demand for more by-products supply for WBP (sawdust, particles, etc.), which implies a reduction wood fuel for energy (pellets, chips).
EU 2014/52/EU Environmental Impact Assessment	Guarantee the protection of the environment and transparency in the decision-making processes of various public and private projects, evaluating human health, biodiversity, natural resources, cultural heritage and their interactions.	Possible reduction of wood supply due to increased administrative and reporting requirements.	Environmental impact assessment is required for thermal power stations, industrial plants for the production of wood pulp and other fibre materials, and paper and cardboard products.

Table 2. EU regulations, main objectives and potential implications for wood supply and demand.